

Dissemination material created and actions developed

Deliverable 11.9

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AUTHORS (REPORT)	Luz María González Soriano (UPO) & Daniel Romero Portillo (UPO)

REVIEWERS	Antonia Maria Ruiz Jimenez (UPO), Katalin Tardos (CSS); Romane Blassel (ECSA); Michèle Amacker (UBERN)
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Executive Summary

Deliverable 11.9 documents the dissemination and communication materials produced, and the actions implemented by the UNTWIST consortium. The project aims to support renewed democratic representation of citizens' heterogeneous gender-related needs through evidence-based, EU values-aligned alternatives to anti-gender narratives. This deliverable provides a formal and auditable account of dissemination outputs, target audiences, and observable results achieved during the project. Developed in coherence with Deliverable D11.4 (Dissemination and Communication Plan), D11.9 operationally complements the strategic framework by reporting the concrete materials and actions implemented in practice. All dissemination activities followed the Project Identity guidelines defined in D11.2, ensuring consistency, recognisability, and coherence across partners, channels, and formats.

Dissemination activities targeted five main stakeholder groups: political parties and political actors; civil society organisations and NGOs; institutions and policymakers at local, national, and EU levels; the scientific community; and citizens and the wider public. Actions and materials were tailored to these audiences according to their roles as users, multipliers, or beneficiaries of UNTWIST research and policy-oriented outputs. Dissemination objectives focused on raising awareness, enabling engagement and co-production, strengthening networks, supporting knowledge transfer, facilitating advocacy through evidence-based recommendations, and contributing to training and capacity-building. These objectives were underpinned by core messages highlighting the legitimacy and diversity of gender-related needs, the democratic risks of representation gaps, and the availability of practical, empirically grounded alternatives aligned with EU values.

Dissemination was implemented through a combination of targeted events, recurring communication outputs, and digital channels. Ongoing dissemination was supported by newsletters, regular activity on X, and a wide range of printed and digital materials, including evidence-based briefings, static infographics, interactive web tools, and Observables designed to enhance accessibility and usability of project findings.

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1. Introduction

This Deliverable 11.9, *Dissemination material created and actions developed*, reports the dissemination and communication materials produced and the actions implemented by the UNTWIST consortium. The overall objective of UNTWIST is to support renewed democratic representation of citizens' heterogeneous gender-related needs and demands through evidence-based, EU values-aligned alternatives to anti-gender narratives.

The purpose of this deliverable is to serve as a formal record and structured overview of the dissemination, communication, or stakeholder engagement strategies and activities developed and implemented throughout the project. It provides a consolidated account of the materials created, the dissemination actions carried out, the targeted stakeholder groups, and the results or outputs that can be documented at this stage.

The intended audience of the dissemination materials and actions developed within the UNTWIST project includes political parties and political actors, civil society organisations and NGOs, institutions and policymakers at local, national and EU levels, the scientific community, and citizens and the wider public. These audiences have been addressed through differentiated materials and actions tailored to their respective roles as potential users, multipliers, or beneficiaries of UNTWIST research results and policy-oriented outputs.

All the dissemination and communication materials and actions reported in this deliverable have been developed and implemented in line with the Project Identity guidelines established in D11.2 (Project website, logo, visual identity, and templates), ensuring consistent branding and coherence across channels, products and partner contributions. This Project Identity establishes the conceptual, narrative and visual foundations of UNTWIST, grounded in a clear articulation of the project's vision and mission and their coherent translation into a shared framework for all communication and dissemination outputs. At a conceptual level, the identity reflects UNTWIST's commitment to recognising the heterogeneity of citizens' gender- and sex-related needs and to promoting democratic, evidence-based and inclusive forms of representation, reinforcing the project's positioning as an EU values-aligned alternative to anti-gender narratives. At a visual and formal level, D11.2 defines common principles for the use of logos,

colours, typography and layouts, designed to symbolically convey ideas of incompleteness, inclusiveness and transformation in gender representation while ensuring recognisability and consistency across all dissemination materials and actions.

1.1. Scope of the document

This deliverable documents the dissemination and communication materials created and the actions developed within the UNTWIST project, describing what they consist of, what they were designed for, who they were designed to reach, and what results are observed or evidenced so far (e.g., outputs produced, channels activated, events held, stakeholder interactions initiated, and early indicators of reach and uptake if available). Accordingly, the scope of the deliverable is to provide a clear and auditable account of the specific dissemination-related implementation carried out by the consortium.

For reasons of proportionality and to avoid duplication, this deliverable does not provide an exhaustive account of dissemination activities primarily addressed to the scientific community (e.g., participation in academic conferences, scientific workshops, and peer-reviewed publications). These scientific dissemination activities are reported through the project's official reporting channels, including the EU Funding and Tenders Portal, where the consortium maintains the corresponding records.

Accordingly, D11.9 focuses on dissemination and communication activities specifically aimed at policy-oriented and practitioner stakeholders, including political parties and political actors, public institutions and policymakers, and civil society organisations and NGOs (as well as broader public-facing outputs insofar as they support stakeholder outreach and uptake).

This deliverable is developed in coherence with Deliverable D11.4 (Dissemination and Communication Plan). While D11.4 establishes the overall project framework, principles, stakeholder mapping, tools, and monitoring approach guiding dissemination and communication, D11.9 operationally complements it by reporting the specific materials and

actions that have been produced and carried out in practice in the UNTWIST project, and by documenting their intended use and observed outputs as of the date of this deliverable.

1.2. Dissemination objectives and strategies

The dissemination materials and actions reported in this deliverable have been developed with specific objectives, audiences and messages in mind. Together, these elements frame how UNTWIST outputs have been communicated and transferred to relevant stakeholders, supporting visibility, knowledge use and policy relevance. The following subsections outline the main goals guiding these activities, identify the stakeholder groups and audiences addressed, and summarise the core messages conveyed through the dissemination materials and actions developed and implemented within the project.

1.2.1. Main goals

The dissemination and communication materials and actions reported in D11.9 have been designed to contribute to the following goals:

Raise awareness: Increase visibility and recognition of UNTWIST, its rationale, and its outputs among relevant stakeholders and broader publics, ensuring clarity about the project's focus and added value.

Engagement and co-production: Support meaningful interaction with stakeholders and citizens, including participatory and co-creation formats that enable feedback, deliberation, and collaborative development of policy-relevant insights.

Networking: Strengthen connections and synergies among relevant organisations and communities (political actors, NGOs, institutions, researchers and practitioners), facilitating sustained relationships that support dissemination, exchange and longer-term uptake.

Knowledge transference: Make results, tools, evidence and data accessible in usable formats and transfer them to potential users, enabling understanding, reuse, and application across contexts and countries.

Advocacy and policy recommendation: Support the circulation and practical usability of evidence-based policy recommendations, enabling stakeholders (especially political actors, policymakers and civil society) to consider and promote “untwisted” policy responses aligned with EU values.

Training and educating: Contribute to capacity-building by producing and disseminating materials that inform, educate, and enhance stakeholder competencies (e.g., understanding gender-related representation gaps, interpreting evidence, and applying recommendations).

1.2.2. Stakeholders and target audiences

Consistent with the stakeholder characterisation in the project, UNTWIST dissemination and communication activities target five primary groups:

Political parties (mainstream and relevant party actors), as key implementers of representation and policy supply in representative democracy.

Civil society organisations and NGOs, including gender equality and democratic advocacy organisations, as multipliers and pressure groups.

Scientific community, including researchers, academics, doctoral and postgraduate communities, as both users and validators of UNTWIST knowledge, tools and data.

Institutions and policymakers, including EU institutions, national and local administrations, and relevant public bodies, as decision-makers and implementers of policy frameworks.

Citizens and wider society, as ultimate beneficiaries, participants in co-creation processes, and recipients of accessible outputs that can reduce “gender fatigue,” improve awareness, and enhance democratic empowerment.

1.2.3. Core messages

UNTWIST dissemination is anchored in a coherent set of core messages, adapted in tone and emphasis to each audience while preserving consistency across outputs:

Heterogeneity and legitimacy: Citizens hold diverse and legitimate gender- and sex-related needs, demands and worries across class, ethnicity, age and other social dimensions; democratic representation should address this heterogeneity rather than ignore it.

Representation gap and vulnerability: When mainstream actors overlook parts of this agenda, right-wing populist actors can occupy the space by reframing concerns through anti-gender narratives that conflict with EU values.

Evidence-based alternatives: There are untwisted, EU values-aligned ways to represent and respond to gender-related concerns; these alternatives can be empirically grounded, politically feasible and adaptable across ideological traditions.

Practical usability: UNTWIST outputs—especially policy briefings and the Toolkit and Policy Recommendations Handbook—are designed to be directly usable by practitioners (parties, policymakers, NGOs) to improve substantive representation and strengthen democracy.

Shared democratic benefit: Improving gender-based representation benefits citizens and democratic quality, reduces polarisation and backlash dynamics, and supports gender equality as a democratic value and lived practice.

2. Dissemination actions

Dissemination actions within the UNTWIST project were implemented through a combination of targeted stakeholder-oriented events, recurring communication outputs, and digital channels. The overall purpose of these actions was to facilitate the effective transfer of project findings and evidence-based messages to relevant policy and practitioner stakeholders, support informed dialogue, and promote the uptake of UNTWIST insights on gender, politics, and democratic representation.

For reasons of proportionality and to avoid duplication, this section does not provide an exhaustive account of dissemination activities primarily addressed to the scientific community, such as participation in academic conferences, scientific workshops, and peer-reviewed publications. These scientific dissemination activities are documented through the project's official reporting channels, including the EU Funding and Tenders Portal.

This section is structured as follows. Section 2.1 reports on the stakeholder-oriented dissemination of events organised or co-organised by the consortium. Section 2.2 covers the project's newsletter as a recurring dissemination tool. Section 2.3 presents UNTWIST's use of social networks as dissemination channels and describes the main content formats used. Section 2.4 outlines the role and development of the UNTWIST website as a central dissemination hub. Finally, Section 2.5 provides an overview of the project's social media accounts and their current status and reach.

2.1. Dissemination events

The UNTWIST project has engaged primarily with policy-oriented and practitioner stakeholders through a series of dissemination events designed to foster dialogue, share evidence-based insights, and support democratic debate around gender and politics. In line with the scope of this deliverable, the events reported in this section are those aimed at political actors and parties, public institutions and policymakers, and civil society organisations and NGOs. Below,

these dissemination events are presented distinguishing between international- and local-level activities.

Overall, stakeholder engagement in this thematic area is intrinsically challenging, as participation is often constrained by limited availability, competing agendas, and the sensitivity of the topic. Consequently, attendance has been moderate despite targeted outreach efforts and dissemination campaigns based on a broad stakeholder contact base. Notwithstanding these constraints, the project successfully organised a series of dissemination events, including two international events and four national events, which are described in detail in the following sections.

2.1.1. International dissemination events

- Untwisting Gender Representation: Evidence-Based Insights for Democratic Renewal

Date: February 13rd, 2025.

Location: Online

Organisers: UNTWIST consortium (jointly organised by all partners).

Target audience: The event targeted political parties and political actors, public institutions and policymakers, civil society organisations/NGOs (with broader interest from the academic community). The event gathered 82 participants.

The recording was uploaded to the project's YouTube channel and has reached 87 views as of the date of this deliverable. (*See Annex, Figure A1.*)

Link: <https://youtu.be/xlUo11rmxuU?si=Bk8e9wHU4WnvM7gx>

- Launch of the UNTWIST Policy Recommendation Handbook: Why Economic Inequalities Have Gendered Consequences for European Democracy

Date: March 18th, 2026.

Location: Hybrid (in-person European Parliament, Brussels; and online)

Organisers: UNTWIST consortium (jointly organised by all partners).

Target audience: The event targeted political actors and policymakers at the European level, public institutions, researchers, civil society organisations, and registered participants interested in gender equality, democratic resilience, and EU public policy. The event gathered 90 participants, with a balanced mix of in-person (35) and online (55) attendance.

Link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=PkNdLCHceP8&t=4952s>

2.1.2. Local dissemination events

- Strengthening democracy through gender equality

Date: November 14th, 2025.

Location: Hybrid (in-person Spanish Congress, Madrid; and online)

Organisers: Pablo de Olavide University (UPO), co-organised with the University of Deusto.

Venue / format: Hybrid event hosted at the Spanish Congress of Deputies (Madrid).

Target audience: Political institutions and parties, policymakers, and civil society organisations (with some participation from academia).

(See Annex, Figure A2.)

Link: https://youtu.be/BJnwe_RPPAA?si=2VP6EaisqWbrcQgs

- Feminism and Democracy

Organiser: Jointly organised in Hungary by the UNTWIST project team together with the Hungarian partners of its sister projects, CCINDLE and Push*Back*Lash.

Venue-format: The event was held as a joint dissemination activity aimed at presenting results and fostering dialogue with key stakeholders. The programme allocated 75 minutes to each project partner. It combined presentations with interactive elements, including a World

Café session organised by the Hungarian UNTWIST team. This participatory component followed the presentation of findings and reflections from two discussants and was designed to gather stakeholder input for policy recommendations.

Target audience: The organisers merged stakeholder databases across the three projects to maximise outreach. Approximately 150 stakeholders were identified, including representatives of mainstream political parties, gender-focused civil society organisations, and relevant experts. More than 60 participants registered for the event.

- *UNTWISTED: Wie politisch sind Genderfragen wirklich?*

Date: March, 5 2026

Location: In person (Saarbrücken)

Organiser: UNTWIST project team (Saarbrücken), with involvement of a colleague from the FIERCE sister project and outreach to WP9 participants.

Venue-format: The event took place in Saarbrücken as a combined dissemination event and policy co-creation meeting. It featured a structured programme (shared in advance with stakeholders), including presentations of the UNTWIST Handbook and key policy recommendations. The format combined dissemination, expert dialogue, and audience engagement. Outreach was supported through social media (Instagram and BlueSky) and direct stakeholder invitations. (*See Annex, Figure A3.*)

Target audience: A total of 30 stakeholders were contacted (11 individuals from previous events and 19 civil society organisations), alongside workshop participants. 53 people registered for the event, of whom 40 attended.

Links:

<https://www.instagram.com/p/DU26zEgCGgi/>

<https://www.instagram.com/p/DUpuSaEDXIE/>

<https://bsky.app/profile/politicsunisaar.bsky.social/post/3mf2j4soads2b>

<https://www.instagram.com/p/DViagjQDfu6/>

<https://www.instagram.com/p/DV0pJS1CNuq/>

- Gender Equality and Democratic Futures in Denmark

Date: Friday, 13 March 2026, 14:00–16:00

Location: Hybrid (in-person Roskilde University, and online)

Organiser: Roskilde University (RUC), in collaboration with the UNTWIST and FIERCE research projects.

Venue–format: The event took place in a hybrid format at Roskilde University (room 25.1-035) and online. It combined presentations, interactive discussion, and a high-level conversation. The programme included presentations of core findings from UNTWIST and FIERCE, an opening participatory discussion, and a featured conversation between Drude Dahlerup and Colm Flaherty. A break and a closing reception provided additional opportunities for informal exchange and networking. Participation was open, with no prior registration required. (*See Annex, Figure A4.*)

Target audience: The event was open to a broad audience, including researchers, civil society organisations, stakeholders, and the general public, with both in-person and online participation options. Targeted outreach was conducted through an updated stakeholder contact list, including political party representatives (both individual and secretariat level), NGOs and civil society organisations (e.g. trade unions), think tanks, and academic stakeholders. Invitations were also circulated to workshop participants.

- Forum for Democracy and Gender Equality (PushBackLash Clustered Event)

Date: 25 September 2025

Location: University of Salzburg, Austria

Organiser: UNIMAN, within the PushBackLash Year 3 Conference

Venue-format: In-person forum integrated into a wider conference, combining panel discussions, interactive sessions (Gender Café), and a closing roundtable

Target audience: Academics and researchers, policymakers, and civil society organisations/NGOs

2.2. Newsletter

The UNTWIST newsletter was introduced as a practical dissemination tool to support knowledge transfer and maintain regular engagement with the project's stakeholder communities. While the newsletter was not initially foreseen in the General Agreement, the consortium subsequently agreed to implement it to strengthen continuity in communication and to provide periodic, accessible updates on project progress and results.

Each issue summarises key developments and findings from completed work packages and highlights ongoing activities, using concise and visually engaging content (Prezi format) to facilitate understanding. The newsletter primarily targets policy-oriented and practitioner stakeholders (political parties and political actors, policymakers and public institutions, and civil society organisations/NGOs) and is also shared more broadly through the project's dissemination channels.

As of the date of this deliverable, six issues of the UNTWIST newsletter have been released. Each issue was distributed to 82 subscribers, and additionally shared via the project website and social media channels,

The issues are:

1. **Newsletter 1 – First Issue** (March , 2024) – [Link](#)
2. **Newsletter 2 – Second Issue** (January, 2025) – [Link](#)
3. **Newsletter 3 – Third Issue** (May, 2025) – [Link](#)

4. **Newsletter 4 – Fourth Issue** (July, 2025) – [Link](#)
5. **Newsletter 5 – Fifth Issue** (November, 2025) – [Link](#)
6. **Newsletter 6 – Sixth Issue** (March, 2026) – [Link](#)

(See Annex, Figure A5, for an illustrative newsletter visual).

2.3. Social networks

This section describes the UNTWIST project’s use of social networks as digital dissemination channels. It outlines the main platforms activated, the types of content published, and the audience targeted—primarily policy-oriented and practitioner stakeholders (e.g., political actors and parties, policymakers and public institutions, and civil society organisations/NGOs), while also supporting broader public visibility where relevant.

The information below is organised in two parts. First, it presents the UNTWIST website as the project’s central digital dissemination hub, outlining its role in providing access to project information, outputs, and updates. Second, it describes the project’s social media accounts, including the main platforms activated, the types of content published (e.g., announcements, project updates, key findings, and event-related communication), and the audiences targeted—primarily policy-oriented and practitioner stakeholders (e.g., political actors and parties, policymakers and public institutions, and civil society organisations/NGOs), while also supporting broader public visibility where relevant. Where available, early indicators of reach and engagement (e.g., followers/subscribers, views, impressions, and interactions) are also reported.

2.3.1. UNTWIST Website

The UNTWIST project website serves as the project’s main digital hub for knowledge transfer and dissemination. It provides open access to general information about the project, its objectives, structure, and consortium, as well as to key public outputs, results, and updates. Unlike social networks, the website is primarily a non-interactive channel; for this reason, it is reported in a dedicated section separate from the project’s social media platforms.

The website is designed to support stakeholder uptake by offering a stable reference point where policy-oriented and practitioner stakeholders can access materials and follow project developments over time. It also supports broader public visibility by centralising news, event-related information, and links to dissemination resources.

The website includes content in English and selected sections in consortium local languages. Local-language content is provided to facilitate access for national and local stakeholders and to reduce language barriers for those engaging with project information and results in their country's contexts.

Link: <https://www.upo.es/investiga/UNTWIST/>

(See Annex, Figure A6).

2.3.2. Social Media accounts

In addition to the dissemination tools described above, the consortium maintained a limited set of official social media and audiovisual accounts to support outreach and facilitate access to project updates and selected outputs. Although these accounts were not initially foreseen in the General Agreement, the consortium subsequently agreed that maintaining dedicated profiles would be beneficial to strengthen dissemination capacity and continuity of communication over time. It should also be noted that the broader context of social media platforms evolved significantly during the project lifecycle—most visibly the transition from Twitter to X and related changes in platform policies and ownership—which affected reach and engagement patterns. Therefore, social media outcomes should be interpreted in light of these external changes.

- UNTWIST Profile on X (General and Spanish)

The general UNTWIST profile on X functions as a key channel for engagement and outreach at the international level. Through this profile, information related to completed work packages,

project milestones, and relevant updates is regularly communicated in English. The account contributes to increasing the project's visibility among policymakers, researchers, civil society actors, and citizens, and has progressively built an audience interested in the project's themes and results.

Link: <https://x.com/UNTWISTproject>

(See Annex, Figure A7).

In parallel, a dedicated Spanish-language profile on X was created to strengthen engagement with Spanish-speaking audiences. This profile shares information on completed work packages and project updates in Spanish, facilitating accessibility to Spanish stakeholders. It complements the general account by ensuring that key messages reach national and regional stakeholders, including institutions, policymakers, and civil society organisations.

Link: https://x.com/UNTWIST_esp

(See Annex, Figure A8).

In other country contexts, partners preferred to amplify dissemination through redistribution and engagement via their institutional, professional, or personal accounts, leveraging existing follower networks rather than creating additional dedicated project profiles.

- UNTWIST YouTube Channel

The UNTWIST YouTube channel was created as a dedicated space for audiovisual dissemination, hosting selected recordings and project-related videos to support knowledge transfer in accessible formats. While the project initially anticipated producing a larger volume of audiovisual materials, dissemination efforts evolved over time and greater emphasis was placed on alternative digital tools (including a more dynamic web-based dissemination approach). As a result, the number of standalone videos produced remained limited, while the channel continued to serve as a repository for selected recordings and audiovisual outputs.

Link: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCdaeM_SYO18Yt8QRaqSO75A

(See Annex, Figure A9).

3. Dissemination materials

This section outlines the assets developed to support dissemination activities.

3.1. Printed materials

This subsection covers dissemination assets produced exclusively in physical format for distribution in face-to-face contexts e.g., meetings, stakeholder events, and outreach activities). These materials are intended for on-site dissemination and are not made available through digital channels.

3.1.1. Notebook

A notebook was developed to foster engagement within the UNTWIST project. Released in June 2024, this A3 booklet includes the project logo and basic project information, reinforcing project visibility in face-to-face contexts. The notebook was distributed at events organised by the consortium, as well as at external events attended by project partners, reaching audiences from academia, political and policymaking spheres, and relevant institutions. This material contributed to raising awareness and engagement among political parties, civil society organisations and NGOs, the scientific community, institutions and policymakers, and the wider public.

(See Annex, Figure A10).

3.1.2. Folder

A folder was developed to foster engagement within the UNTWIST project. Released in June 2024, it brings together basic information about the project, along with its vision, mission, and strategy, helping to contextualise the project's objectives and approach. The folder was distributed at events organised by the consortium, as well as at external events attended by project partners, reaching audiences from academia, political and policymaking spheres, and relevant institutions. This material contributed to raising awareness and engagement among political parties, civil society organisations and NGOs, the scientific community, institutions and policymakers, and the wider public.

(See Annex, Figure A11).

3.2. Mixed materials

This subsection covers dissemination assets that are produced in digital format and made available through the project's online channels, in particular the UNTWIST project website. When relevant for face-to-face outreach, these materials may also be printed and distributed in physical form at events and stakeholder meetings. This mixed-format approach supports both online accessibility and in-person dissemination.

3.2.1. Flyer

A flyer was developed to foster engagement within the UNTWIST project. Released in September 2024, it provides basic information about the project, along with its vision, mission, and strategy. The flyer is available in multiple languages (English, Spanish, Danish, German, and Hungarian), supporting dissemination among diverse audiences. It was distributed at events organised by the consortium and at external events attended by project partners, reaching audiences from academia, political and policymaking spheres, and relevant institutions, as well as the wider public.

(See Annex, Figure A12).

3.2.2. Poster

A poster was developed to support engagement activities within the UNTWIST project. Released in July 2024, it presents basic project information, contact details, and the project logo, contributing to clear visual identification. The poster was shown at events organised by the consortium and at external events attended by project partners, involving academics, politicians, policymakers and relevant institutions, and reinforcing the project's visibility among its target audiences.

(See Annex, Figure A13).

3.2.3. Briefings

During the project, five evidence-based UNTWIST briefings were produced to provide policy-oriented and practitioner stakeholders with concise, actionable recommendations grounded in project research. The briefings are structured as short PDF documents, each linked to specific work packages (WPs) and designed to translate key findings into practical guidance for organisations, political actors and parties, public institutions, and policymakers.

As a dissemination asset, the briefings are available in digital format and distributed through the project's online channels (including public repositories/links and the project website, where applicable). They are also formatted so that they can be printed and used in face-to-face dissemination contexts (e.g., stakeholder meetings and events) when relevant. In line with the project's outreach approach, selected briefings have been prepared and/or made available in additional languages to facilitate accessibility for national and local stakeholders where needed.

The briefings produced are listed below, together with their public links and early indicators of uptake (downloads) where available:

1. **UNTWIST Briefing 01 – Recommendations for Gender-Based Policy-Making: A Typology of Gender-Based Needs** (November 25, 2024) – [Zenodo Link](#) – WP1 – 59 downloads
2. **UNTWIST Briefing 02 – Strengthening Democracy by Improving Gender Representation** (November 26, 2024) – [Zenodo Link](#) – WP2 – 84 downloads
3. **UNTWIST Briefing 03 – Representing Voters' Needs: A Guide on Gender and Public Opinion Data** (November 27, 2024) – [Zenodo Link](#) – WP3 – 75 downloads
4. **UNTWIST Briefing 04 – Party Priorities and Positions on Gender-Related Issues** (November 28, 2024) – [Zenodo Link](#) – WP4 – 85 downloads
5. **UNTWIST Briefing 06 – Distinct Grievance Pathways to the Populist Radical Right: The Gender Dimension in Contemporary Europe** (March 24, 2025) – [Zenodo Link](#) – WP8 – 0 downloads

Overall, these briefings contributed to the project's policy recommendation objectives by making research findings accessible in a practical format and supporting the translation of evidence into actionable guidance for key stakeholders.

3.3. Digital materials

This subsection covers dissemination assets produced exclusively in digital format. These materials are made available through the project's online channels, including the UNTWIST project website and its official social media platforms, and are not intended for print-only distribution.

The information below is organised as follows. First, it summarises the project's regular social media communication activity on X, including language coverage and posting frequency. Second, it reports event-related (special) social media communication used to promote and document key dissemination moments. Any illustrative screenshots are provided in the Annex.

3.3.1. Social Media content

- Posts on X (Twitter)

Throughout the duration of the project, regular content has been published on X in both English and Spanish through the UNTWIST profiles. Posts have typically been published at least twice per week and have been structured around communication packages derived from completed deliverables and project milestones. This sustained activity supports continuous engagement with target audiences and contributes to both quantitative reach and qualitative interaction with policy-oriented stakeholders, civil society organisations, and interested broader audiences.

As of March 31, 2026, a total of 358 posts had been published via the general UNTWIST profile and 336 via the Spanish-language profile.

In addition to regular posting, the project also produced event-related social media communication to increase visibility for key dissemination events and outputs (e.g., announcements, reminders, live/event coverage, and post-event highlights). Where screenshots are included for illustration, they are provided in the Annex.

Special Event Posts on X (Twitter):

25N Campaign: United Against Sexual and Gender-Based Violence – FIERCE Campaign. The 25N Campaign was launched on 24 November 2026 as part of the UNTWIST project’s engagement and co-production activities. This digital initiative consisted of a social media post aimed at raising awareness and mobilizing action against sexual and gender-based violence.

8th March Campaign from Sister Projects: Our claims for an engendered Democracy. The 8th March Campaign from Sister Projects: *Our Claims for an Engendered Democracy* was launched as a joint initiative with the project’s sister projects to mark International Women’s Day. Developed within the framework of UNTWIST’s engagement and co-production activities, the campaign aimed to highlight and reaffirm the ongoing need to continue fighting for women’s rights and gender equality in democratic systems. The initiative took the form of a digital social media post published on X, using an animated GIF to convey key messages in a dynamic and accessible way.

(See Annex, Figure A14).

- Audiovisual materials – Project videos (hosted on the UNTWIST YouTube channel)

The UNTWIST project produced a set of short audiovisual materials to support knowledge transfer in an accessible format. These videos are hosted on the project’s official YouTube channel and are intended to complement written dissemination materials by providing concise project introductions and event-related content for policy-oriented stakeholders, civil society organisations, and broader interested audiences.

1. Video: “UNTWIST Project – Introduction”

This introductory video presents the UNTWIST project, outlining its objectives, vision, and mission in a concise and accessible manner. It is designed as an entry point for a broad audience, including citizens, civil society organisations, and policymakers, and is available in the consortium’s working languages.

Link: <https://youtu.be/wYWlFqLs7RI?si=DfK84fVIdS1HqSzu>

2. Video: “Jornada de presentación de resultados UNTWIST: Fortalecer la democracia desde la igualdad de género”

This video documents the conference on Strengthening Democracy through Gender Equality, held at the Spanish Congress of Deputies. The main language of the video is Spanish, while the interventions of the invited speakers are in English. The recommendations presented have been adapted to the Spanish context. The video showcases key UNTWIST project results and serves as a dissemination tool to raise awareness about the project's evidence-based contributions to democratic renewal from a gender equality perspective. It targets policymakers, political actors, the scientific community, and civil society organisations.

Link: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BJnwe_RPPAA&t=2866s

3. Video: “Jornada de presentación de resultados UNTWIST: Fortalecer la democracia desde la igualdad de género” (Spanish version)

This Spanish-language version of the conference video has the same content as the original, with the only difference that the interventions of the invited speakers originally in English are translated into Spanish. This enhances accessibility for policymakers, institutions, and civil society actors at the national level. The video reinforces the dissemination of key project messages on gender equality and democratic strengthening.

Link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zjLQ3ZohAxs&t=2673s>

4. Video: “Untwisting Gender Representation: Evidence-Based Insights for Democratic Renewal”

This video corresponds to a UNTWIST dissemination event held in February 2025 and focuses on presenting evidence-based insights on gender representation and democratic renewal. It supports knowledge transfer by translating research findings into an accessible audiovisual format aimed at policymakers, the scientific community, and relevant stakeholders.

Link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xIUo11rmxuU>

5. Video: “UNTWIST at the European Parliament | Policy Recommendation Handbook Launch”

This video documents the launch event of the UNTWIST Policy Recommendation Handbook at the European Parliament. It presents the main findings of the three-year Horizon Europe project, highlighting how anti-gender politics should be understood not only as a cultural backlash, but also in relation to material insecurity and everyday economic inequalities. The video serves as a dissemination tool aimed at policymakers, researchers, and civil society actors, promoting the project's evidence-based recommendations to strengthen democratic resilience in Europe.

Link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=PkNdLCHceP8&t=4954s>

- Static Infographics

The project developed a set of static infographics as digital dissemination materials to present key findings in an accessible, visually engaging format. These infographics were designed to support knowledge transfer beyond technical reporting by summarising results, concepts, and empirical patterns in standalone visuals that can be easily shared and re-used across communication channels.

The infographics were made available through the project's digital ecosystem, including publication on the UNTWIST website and dissemination via the project's social media channels. In addition, selected infographics were also featured and circulated through the UNTWIST newsletter, supporting continuity of outreach and providing stakeholders with curated visual summaries alongside project updates. Overall, the static infographics targeted policy-oriented and practitioner stakeholders (political actors and parties, policymakers and public institutions, and civil society organisations/NGOs), while also supporting broader public visibility where relevant.

The static infographics produced are organised below by the work package.

1. WP1 Static Infographics

The project developed a series of static infographics to support engagement and dissemination of WP1 findings. These graphics provide detailed information pieces to help audiences better

understand the project's work in this area. They were shared on X to complement social media messages and ensure visual support for the communication of key insights. The infographics include:

1. **Four Perspectives for Gender-Based Policymaking** – [Link-Eng](#) & [Link-Spa](#)
2. **Data Analysis. Typology Development** – [Link-Eng](#) & [Link-Spa](#)
3. **Data Collection. Literature Review to Build the Typology** – [Link-Eng](#) & [Link-Spa](#)
4. **Methodology** – [Link-Eng](#) & [Link-Spa](#)
5. **Results Overview** – [Link-Eng](#) & [Link-Spa](#)
6. **Findings that Make Up the Toolbox of the UNTWIST Typology** – [Link-Eng](#) & [Link-Spa](#)
7. **Ideal Types I** – [Link-Eng](#) & [Link-Spa](#)
8. **Ideal Types II** – [Link-Eng](#) & [Link-Spa](#)
9. **The Typology. Uses, Relevance and Value** – [Link-Eng](#) & [Link-Spa](#)

These infographics were targeted at political parties, civil society organisations, the scientific community, institutions, policymakers, and the wider public.

2. WP2 Static Infographics

A second set of static infographics was developed for WP2, supporting engagement and providing visual material to accompany social media posts during the dissemination period. These graphics explore narratives from focus groups and national-specific topics:

1. **Cross-Cutting Themes in the Focus Groups** – [Link-Eng](#) & [Link-Spa](#)
2. **Narratives in the Focus Groups: Emancipation Fatigue** – [Link-Eng](#) & [Link-Spa](#)
3. **Narratives in the Focus Groups: Reinterpretation of Roles** – [Link-Eng](#) & [Link-Spa](#)
4. **Narratives in Focus Groups: Women's Participation in the Labour Market** – [Link-Eng](#) & [Link-Spa](#)
5. **Narratives in Focus Groups: Different Stances on LGTBIQ+** – [Link-Eng](#) & [Link-Spa](#)
6. **Narratives in Focus Groups: Dissonances Around Feminism** – [Link-Eng](#) & [Link-Spa](#)
7. **National Specific Topics: Denmark** – [Link-Eng](#) & [Link-Spa](#)
8. **National Specific Topics: Hungary** – [Link-Eng](#) & [Link-Spa](#)
9. **National Specific Topics: Spain** – [Link-Eng](#) & [Link-Spa](#)

10. **National Specific Topics: Switzerland** – [Link-Eng](#) & [Link-Spa](#)

11. **National Specific Topics: UK** – [Link-Eng](#) & [Link-Spa](#)

12. **National Specific Topics: Germany** – [Link-Eng](#) & [Link-Spa](#)

These infographics were aimed at the same broad audience as WP1, supporting a more detailed understanding of project findings and fostering engagement across different national contexts.

3. WP3 Static Infographics

Finally, WP3 infographics provide visual material to support dissemination of survey and political analysis results. These graphics were shared during the dissemination period on X, offering detailed insights into international and national surveys on gender, as well as political themes:

1. **How Do International Surveys Measure Gender?** – [Link-Eng](#) & [Link-Spa](#)

2. **How Do National Surveys Measure Gender?** – [Link-Eng](#) & [Link-Spa](#)

3. **Political Themes in International Surveys on Gender** – [Link-Eng](#) & [Link-Spa](#)

4. **Political Themes in National Surveys on Gender** – [Link-Eng](#) & [Link-Spa](#)

These materials are designed to provide a more detailed understanding of WP3 findings, targeting political parties, civil society organisations, the scientific community, institutions, policymakers, and the wider public.

3.3.2. Interactive webs

During the project, a series of interactive web applications were developed to present the main findings of each Work Package (WP) in a visually engaging and dynamic way. These tools allow users to explore data and insights from the project, facilitating understanding and encouraging engagement among a broad audience that includes political parties, civil society organisations, scientific communities, institutions, policymakers, and the wider public. The interactive format provides an intuitive, user-friendly way to navigate the project's evidence and results, supporting both knowledge transfer and coproduction activities.

The interactive webs are:

1. WP1 – Why do we need a typology of gender-based needs? – [Access here](#)
2. WP2 – Which are RWPP switcher voters’ gender-based needs? – [Access here](#)
3. WP3 – What do surveys ask about gender-based needs? – [Access here](#)
4. WP4 – How do European parties engage with gender-based needs? – [Access here](#)
5. WP8 – How do gendered grievances shape support for the populist radical right in Europe? – [Access here](#)

These interactive applications complement other dissemination materials, offering a hands-on approach to project findings that enhances accessibility, promotes engagement, and provides stakeholders with a direct way to explore the evidence generated by UNTWIST. Analytics data for user interactions can be requested from VIT to further assess impact.

3.3.3. Observables

To complement the interactive webs, the UNTWIST project developed a series of interactive Observables for each Work Package, providing a concise, visual, and interactive presentation of the project’s findings. These online tools allow stakeholders—including political parties, civil society organisations, researchers, policymakers, and the wider public—to explore the project’s data in a dynamic and accessible way, enhancing understanding and engagement with the research results.

The Observables produced are:

1. **WP1: A Typology of Gender-Based Needs** – [Explore here](#)
2. **WP2: UNTWIST Focus Groups with RWPP voters** – [Explore here](#)
3. **WP3: Mapping the Representation of Sex/Gender and Gender-Based Needs in Public Opinion Surveys** – [Explore here](#)
4. **WP4: Gender in Party Politics, an Interactive Tool to Explore How Parties Address Gender-Related Issues in Their Manifestos** – [Explore here](#)
5. **WP5: UNTWIST’s Exploration of the Demand and Supply Sides of Gendered Policies** – [Explore here](#)
6. **WP8 Observable: UNTWIST survey** – [Explore here](#)

These Observables serve as a complement to both the project's briefings and the interactive webs, enabling users to interact directly with data and findings, and supporting the project's knowledge transfer and engagement objectives.

Table 1. Overview of Materials Used Across Dissemination Actions

		Events	Newsletters	Website	Profile on X	YouTube Channel
Print	Notebook	✓				
	Folder	✓				
Mixed	Flyer	✓		✓		
	Poster	✓		✓		
Digital	Social Media posts				✓	
	Briefings	✓	✓	✓		✓
	Interactive webs	✓	✓	✓		✓
	Observables	✓	✓	✓		✓

4. Conclusions

Deliverable 11.9 provides a structured and auditable overview of the dissemination materials produced and the actions implemented by the UNTWIST consortium, demonstrating a coherent effort to translate research outputs into accessible formats for diverse stakeholders groups. Across the project, dissemination has been guided by clear objectives—awareness raising, engagement, networking, knowledge transfer, advocacy, and capacity building—while remaining aligned with the Project Identity framework defined in D11.2. This consistency has supported recognisability and coherence across channels, products, and partner contributions.

The consortium deployed a balanced mix of dissemination actions, combining targeted events, regular communication outputs, and digital channels. High-level and policy-relevant events created structured opportunities for dialogue and exchange. These formats enabled direct interaction between research teams and key audiences—including political parties, institutions, civil society organisations, and academia—while strengthening the connection between research evidence and policy debates. Recordings uploaded to the project’s YouTube channel extended the availability of these materials beyond the live events and contributed to sustained, albeit moderate, engagement over time.

In parallel, the project established stable dissemination routines through newsletters and social media. Newsletters issues were distributed to a consistent subscriber database, supporting continuity in outreach to professional audiences. The sustained frequency of posts on X, complemented by the production of extensive infographic series for multiple work packages, indicates sustained efforts to circulate findings in digestible forms and to maintain visibility throughout the project’s duration.

The range of dissemination materials reflects a deliberate strategy to address both face-to-face and online engagement needs. Printed assets (notebooks, folders, flyers, posters) supported visibility and interaction in event settings, while digital tools such as briefings, interactive webs, and Observables provided pathways for deeper engagement with the project’s evidence base. The production of generic and localised briefings further indicates an intention to increase usability

by adapting recommendations to national contexts, although publication and analytics are still pending for several countries, which currently limits the assessment of uptake.

Overall, the evidence suggests that dissemination actions have been implemented in a professional, coherent manner and have achieved steady reach within specialised target groups. At the same time, the results point to opportunities for improvement, particularly in strengthening engagement beyond already-interested communities, consolidating analytics across platforms, and enhancing follow-up mechanisms that support longer-term uptake of tools and recommendations.

5. Annexes

Figure A1. Online dissemination event screenshot (welcome slide). Screenshot from the high-level online stakeholder-oriented dissemination event “*Untwisting Gender Representation: Evidence-Based Insights for Democratic Renewal*” (13 February 2025).

Source: UNTWIST consortium.

Figure A2. Hybrid dissemination event (illustrative visual / slide). Illustrative visual material from the hybrid stakeholder-oriented dissemination event *“Strengthening democracy through gender equality / Fortalecer la democracia desde la igualdad de género”* hosted at the Spanish Congress of Deputies, Madrid (14 November 2025).

Source: UPO / UNTWIST consortium.

Figure A3. Poster for the UNTWIST event: How political are gender issues really?// „Wie politisch sind Genderfragen wirklich?“

Figure A4. Poster and agenda for the UNTWIST event: Gender Equality and Democratic Futures in Denmark

Gender Equality and Democratic Futures in Denmark

Friday 13 March, kl 14-16
25.1-035 and online

Gender equality has become a political battleground, in policy, in the media, and in everyday life. What happens to democracy when gender equality is contested, and what strategies do we need?

This event brings together researchers, civil society organisations, and stakeholders for presentations, dialogue and open discussion. We present core findings from two research projects on gender and democracy in Denmark, UNTWIST and FIERCE.

You can also participate online - scan this QR code or [register here](#).

Everybody welcome, registration not necessary.
We hope you will join us!

For inquiries, please contact the Danish project leader Laura Horn (lhorn@ruc.dk).

RUC Roskilde University

Programme

14.00 Welcome (Laura Horn, RUC)

14.15 Let's start the discussion - What do gender equality and democracy mean in your organisation or daily life?

14.30 UNTWIST: What are citizens telling us about gender and democracy? (Laura Horn)

14.50 FIERCE: Køn under pres: Antifeminisme i Danmark og feministiske strategier i praksis (Susi Meret, Aalborg University, online)

Break with coffee/tea and cake

15.25 Drude Dahlerup & Colm Flaherty in conversation:
What does gender equality mean in Denmark?

15.45 Summing up and tak for i dag

16.00 Join us for the Reception with bubbles and finger food

This event is funded by the EU Horizon UNTWIST project (grant agreement 101060836)

Figure A5. Newsletter visual (illustrative promotional material). Illustrative visual material used to promote the UNTWIST newsletter series.

Source: UNTWIST consortium.

Figure A6. UNTWIST project website (home page) — screenshot. Screenshot of the UNTWIST project website page used as the project’s main digital dissemination hub.

Source: UNTWIST consortium.

Figure A7. UNTWIST profile on X (general/international) — screenshot. Screenshot of the UNTWIST general profile on X.

Source: UNTWIST consortium.

Figure A8. UNTWIST profile on X (Spanish-language) — screenshot. Screenshot of the UNTWIST Spanish-language profile on X.

Source: UNTWIST consortium.

Figure A9. UNTWIST YouTube channel — screenshot. Screenshot of the UNTWIST YouTube channel main page.

Source: UNTWIST consortium.

Figure A10. Printed material — UNTWIST notebook (merchandise). Photograph/image of the UNTWIST branded notebook distributed in face-to-face dissemination contexts.

Source: UNTWIST consortium.

Figure A11. Printed material — UNTWIST folder (merchandise). Photograph/image of the UNTWIST branded folder distributed in face-to-face dissemination contexts.

SUMMARY of UNTWIST

Human beings are highly heterogeneous. Citizens have different needs, demands and worries related to their gender and sex, which are diverse across social classes, ethnicities, ages, etc. All of them are legitimate and deserve to be adequately addressed by political representatives. However, mainstream parties have disregarded some, and right-wing populist actors are twisting their responses contrary to the EU's core values. UNTWIST will find ways to answer needs, demands, and worries related to gender and sex in untwisted ways aligned with the EU's core values. Furthermore, UNTWIST will empower parties to improve their representation of the gender-based interests of the citizenry through the definition, enhancement and transfer of a policy recommendation handbook with evidence-based policy recommendations.

OUR VISION

UNTWIST looks forward to contributing to the construction of a renewed democratic society in which heterogeneous gender needs, demands and worries are all addressed by different parties in democratic ways. Therefore, in our Vision, anti-gender messages from right-wing populist actors are less appealing to citizens because different parties offer alternative ways, respectful and aligned with EU's values, of representing the heterogeneous gender needs, demands and worries of citizens.

OUR MISSION

UNTWIST's primary strategy to reach its Vision is facilitating political actors, particularly parties, 'untwisted' ways of representing gender needs, demands and worries. This transference of knowledge will be done through a policy recommendation handbook with evidence-based policy recommendations.

To develop the policy recommendation handbook, UNTWIST produces a noticeable large quantity of empirical evidence to test its assumptions and hypotheses regarding the factors that make the anti-gender messages of right-wing populist actors attractive to voters. Once they are tested, UNTWIST looks forward to new ways of representing the gender needs, demands and fear previously disregarded by mainstream parties and pick-up, and twisted against EU's values, by right-wing populist actors. We untwist gender representation using citizens' science methodologies.

A key element in UNTWIST's mission is the involvement of political actors mainly and civil society organizations. Communication and transference are essential. UNTWIST needs political actors to incorporate untwisted ways to answer the gender fears, needs and demands of current right-wing populist actors' voters for its Vision to become a reality.

OBJECTIVES AND STRATEGIES

UNTWIST has four main objectives:

1. First, test the hypothesis that mainstream parties are not representing a large set of gender and feminism-related worries, needs and demands. This finding will support the idea that right-wing populist actors act as niche parties. And, more generally, the notion that voters could be brought back to mainstream parties by improving gender representation.
2. Second, test the importance of sex and gender attitudes on voting behaviour. It should allow us to focus on citizens' profiles who can be more successfully targeted. Furthermore, it should also point us toward the more critical areas of gender representation that must be addressed.
3. Third, find untwisted ways to represent gender needs and demands and answer gender worries, turning them into political recommendations.
4. Fourth, involve political actors, mainly political parties, in implementing UNTWIST's policy recommendations.

These objectives are completed through the following work packages:

Fig. 1. UNTWIST's workpackages structure.

Workpackages one to five are related to the first objective: determining how mainstream parties represent gender needs and demands and testing if right-wing populist actors act as niche parties. Workpackages six to eight focus on the second objective. They test the rationality of voters and the importance of gender needs and demands as well as male and female traits in voting behaviour. Workpackages nine and ten focus on the third objective: finding untwisted ways of representing gender needs and demands and making policy recommendations, including how to communicate. Work package eleven focuses on the fourth objective. It is crucial because it aims to involve stakeholders in the project from the beginning and facilitate transference and exploitation of results. Finally, package twelve ensures that we keep on track and everything is done correctly.

Source: UNTWIST consortium.

Figure A12. Mixed material — UNTWIST flyer. UNTWIST project flyer (example layout), available in digital format (and printable for face-to-face dissemination).

SUMMARY of UNTWIST

Human beings are highly heterogeneous. Citizens have different needs, demands and wishes related to their gender and sex, which are diverse across social classes, activities, ages, etc. All of them are legitimate and deserve to be adequately addressed by political representatives, however, mainstream parties have aligned around an anti-right-wing populist action overlooking their responses contrary to the EU's core values. UNTWIST will first aim to assess needs, demands and wishes related to gender and sex in unbalanced ways aligned with the EU's core values. Furthermore, UNTWIST will engage parties to improve their representation of the gender-based interests of the citizenry through the definition, advancement and transfer of a policy recommendation handbook with evidence-based policy recommendations.

OUR VISION

UNTWIST seeks forward to contributing to the transformation of present-day democratic society in what heterogeneous gender needs, demands and wishes are all addressed by different parties in democratic ways. Therefore, in our vision, anti-gender messages from right-wing populist actors are less appealing to citizens because different parties offer alternative ways, respectful and aligned with EU's values, of representing the heterogeneous gender needs, demands and wishes of citizens.

OUR MISSION

UNTWIST's primary strategy to reach its vision is building political action, particularly gender-led, "unbiased" ways of representing gender needs, demands and wishes. The transference of knowledge will be done through a policy recommendation handbook with evidence-based policy recommendations.

To develop the policy recommendation handbook, UNTWIST produces a necessary large quantity of empirical evidence to test its assumptions and hypotheses regarding the factors that make the anti-gender messages of right-wing populist actors attractive to voters. Once they are tested, UNTWIST tools forward to meet needs of representing the gender needs, demands and wishes previously overlooked by mainstream parties and citizens and tested against EU's values by right-wing populist actors, the unbalanced gender representation using evidence-based methodologies.

A key element in UNTWIST's mission is the achievement of public actors, mainly social and minority organizations. Communication and partnerships are essential. UNTWIST needs political actors to implement and evaluate ways to ensure the gender focus, needs and demands of current right-wing populist actors for its vision to become a reality.

OBJECTIVES AND STRATEGIES

UNTWIST has four main objectives:

1. First, and the hypothesis that mainstream parties are not responding to a large set of gender and feminist representation needs and demands. This finding will support the need for right-wing populist actors and its main parties. And, more generally, the reason four values (solidarity, justice, equality, and respect) for representing gender representation.
2. Second, test the importance of sex and gender attitudes on voting behaviour. It should allow us to focus on voters' profiles and test for more accurate EU's objectives. Furthermore, it should also point out toward the most critical needs of gender representation that must be addressed.
3. Third, find alternative ways to represent gender needs and demands and answer gender wishes, turning them into political recommendations.
4. Fourth, assess political actors, mainly political parties, in representing UNTWIST's goals, methodologies.

These objectives are completed through the following main strategies:

WP 1: Project Management

WP 2: Communication, dissemination and evaluation

Workpackages one to five are related to the first objective: determining how mainstream parties represent gender needs and demands and testing if right-wing populist actors and its main parties. Workpackage six to eight focus on the second objective: they test the rationality of voters and the importance of gender needs and demands as well as male and female traits in voting behaviour. Workpackages nine and ten focus on the third objective: finding unbalanced areas of representing gender needs and demands and making policy recommendations, including how to communicate. Work package eleven focuses on the fourth objective: it is crucial because it aims to involve stakeholders in the project from the beginning and facilitate transparency and evaluation of results. Finally, package twelve ensures that we keep on track and everything is done correctly.

Source: UNTWIST consortium.

Figure A13. Mixed material — UNTWIST poster. UNTWIST project poster (example layout), used for visual identification and dissemination in event-based contexts (printable from a digital master file).

Source: UNTWIST consortium.

Figure A14. Special event posts on X — 25N campaign visuals (example). Example of campaign visuals disseminated via the UNTWIST profiles on X as part of a special-event communication initiative (25N campaign: United Against Sexual and Gender-Based Violence).

Source: UNTWIST consortium.

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UNTWIST CONSORTIUM

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CONTACT

untwist@upo.es

www.upo.es/investiga/UNTWIST

